

Spanish Search Pilot

Technical Report

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Introduction

Multilingual access to metadata and contents is of particular interest for Europeana, as our collections are in multiple languages, and our users come from different countries and have different cultural backgrounds. Europeana has defined a medium-term Multilingual Strategy¹ for the improvement of multilingual experiences on the Europeana website.

That includes the design and implementation of a multilingual information retrieval (MLIR) system. This approach is breaking new ground for the cultural sector, so significant experimentation is necessary to find the best ways of approaching the work. With that purpose, we have implemented a prototype called *Spanish pilot*. It has been set up in an external environment that allows users to seamlessly search collections with Spanish or English metadata, using Spanish for querying and returning results also in English. A big portion of the work done will contribute directly to the multilingual system, and the results obtained will help us focus on the main issues to solve.

The prototype can be tested live at <https://search-api-test-lang-portal.eanadev.org/es/> (now in production at <https://www.europeana.eu/es>). Regarding the evaluation conducted, the Solr Metadata collection used is internally available at http://reindex.eanadev.org:9393/solr/search_test/, while the samples of the queries, the scripts and the results of the evaluation are available at http://rnd-2.eanadev.org/home/mmarrero/experiments/crosslingual_SpanishPilot. The data used in the final evaluation is also publicly available at https://rnd-2.eanadev.org/share/crosslingual_SpanishPilot/. The prototype developed in order to be integrated in the Search API is available at <https://github.com/marrerom/emodules>.

State of the Art

MLIR is still a challenge in the area of Information Retrieval, and it is one of the most relevant topics addressed in academia that has a big impact in digital libraries (Agosti 2019). However, in practice, the descriptions of digital objects in the digital collections, as well as the tools for their access and retrieval, remain largely monolingual, despite the evidence that the audience is multilingual (Matusiak et al. 2015) and thus could be interested in results beyond their native language. This is also supported by Stiller et al. (2013), who analyzed 31 CH digital libraries and observed that MLIR is rarely implemented beyond the interface language. Only a few practical cases have been reported in the literature (see extensive reviews in Vassilakaki and Garoufallou (2013),

¹ <https://pro.europeana.eu/post/europeana-dsi-4-multilingual-strategy>

Diekema (2012), and Chen (2004)), and most of them use human translations and specialized multilingual CH vocabularies -or aligned monolingual ones. This is the case for example of the World Digital Library (Oudenaren 2012), which provides access to its contents through item-level metadata records manually translated into seven languages, or the International Children's Digital Library², where the interface and contents are translated by volunteers. Matusiak et al. (2015) reports an experiment using Google Translate to translate to English a collection of Chinese artworks, but they finally opted for human translation given the limitations found with that approach. Also in the CH domain, Kools et al. (2013) obtained satisfactory results with the machine translation of queries in/to English, German and French.

A more recent experiment in Europeana shows the risks of adopting such systems (Marrero et al. 2021), and confirmed some of the main problems already identified in the literature (Stiller et al. 2010; Peters et al. 2012; España-Bonet et al. 2018): the ambiguity of the queries given the lack of context, and the issues of the translation system when dealing with named entities. These issues are especially relevant in digital libraries, where queries and metadata are usually very limited in terms of context -which also makes language detection, when required, harder. The domain is also very specific to apply general translation tools, and the resources are limited to create the appropriate language resources required. As noted by Stiller and Petras (2016), machine translations should be used with care especially for highly specialized and curated content.

In other domains though, machine translation seems to work well. It has been reported that when the pair of languages includes English and one of the most widely spoken languages (such as Spanish, German, or French), currently available machine-translation systems offer high effectiveness from an IR point of view (Dolamic and Savoy 2010). An analysis of the multilingual ad-hoc retrieval task at CLEF (Conference and Labs of the Evaluation Forum) between 2000 and 2009 shows that there is only a decrease of performance of 5-12% compared to the monolingual setting when using machine translation in such circumstances (Savoy and Braschler 2019). España-Bonet et al. (2018) obtained good results in an academic search engine in psychology using specialized dictionaries to automatically translate the queries (average adequacy of 1.4 out of 2), but the experiments showed that machine translation applied to the documents obtained better results in retrieval (Stiller et al. 2019). Regarding the best strategy to adopt, — document translation, query translation or both —, the literature shows that document translation is consistently more effective (Savoy and Braschler 2019; Peters et al. 2012; Stiller et al. 2019), however Savoy and Braschler (2019) report that the performance differences between query translation and document translation

² <http://en.childrenslibrary.org>

approaches vary greatly depending on the query. They suggest taking advantage of both translation models in a hybrid approach: in an experiment run using English as a pivot language, the results obtained outperformed other strategies. This strategy is also more scalable than document translation when the number of different languages is considerable, as is the case in Europeana

Approach

We adopt for the pilot the strategy of query translation, where the queries from the Europeana Spanish portal are translated to English. This step is part of the use of English as a pivot language, as described in the Europeana multilingual strategy, and it can be already implemented given that part of the Europeana metadata contains English data (provided by Cultural Heritage Institutions or resulting from enrichment). We use the metadata that Europeana has gathered. The metadata follows the EDM model³, where the main fields are indexed using Apache Solr⁴. The schema and configuration used is publicly available in Github⁵.

Figure 1. Multilingual approach. In green, tasks implemented in the Spanish pilot.

Figure 1 above is adapted from the Europeana Multilingual Strategy, and shows that we have opted for focusing on a subset of all steps envisioned for multilingual search. We split the process into three different tasks, for which we can report results individually:

- Real-time detection of search query language

³ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>

⁴ <https://solr.apache.org/>

⁵ https://github.com/europeana/search/tree/master/solr_confs/metadata/conf

- Real-time translation of search query
- Construction of multilingual search string and retrieval of the results

We use the Google Cloud Translation API⁶ (Google Translation in the following) for the language identification and translation applied to the queries. The English translation of the query is then used in the construction of the multilingual query that is going to be used to retrieve the search results.

Only for evaluation purposes, we additionally used the CEF Translation service (eTranslation)⁷ to compare the quality of the translations. It was compared using the language automatically identified by the Google translation API (eTranslation does not include this service), or Spanish as source language, given that the latter is the expected language of a user accessing the Europeana Spanish portal.

These services are not applied to the whole queries: we developed an ad-hoc query parser that identifies those parts of the query that are susceptible to be sent together to the language identification or translation service. The parser is based on the Lucene Query Parser⁸, which is the one currently used in the Solr Metadata collection to process the queries, and it has been implemented using regular expressions. More technical information can be found in *Annex C. Query Parser*.

Data

In order to run an evaluation for the three tasks described above, we collected the queries issued from the Europeana Spanish portal from 1st December 2020 to 28th February 2021. From the 34,902 different query strings obtained, we created a stratified sample of 300 queries (more information in *Annex B. Sampling*).

The Solr Metadata collection to be queried contains the metadata of more than 62 million cultural heritage objects provided by museums, libraries, and archives located mainly in Europe. Although the data has not been translated to English, a good portion of the collection is already in English: 39.8% of the documents contain at least one descriptive metadata field tagged in English, while for Spanish that happens only in 0.8% of the collection⁹. This number increases to 78.8% and 61.8% respectively when we include metadata elements for contextual resources (i.e., *skos:Concept*, *edm:Place*,

⁶ <https://cloud.google.com/translate>

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/cefdigital/wiki/display/CEFDIGITAL/eTranslation>

⁸ https://solr.apache.org/guide/7_7/the-standard-query-parser.html

⁹ List of indexed fields and its occurrence available here:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Jz_DcLeFXl2_u4CHmflyIMsjmfbwXL4AVCVe6ZYY1AA/

edm:TimeSpan, *edm:Agent*) from our Entity Collection¹⁰ or from other vocabularies. Additionally, we know that the language of the provider¹¹ is Spanish in 5.5% of the documents, while it is English for 17.5%.

Real-time detection of search query language

When a query is issued in the Solr Metadata collection, the first step consists in the identification of its language. This is done together with the translation step, both in real-time: once the query parser has identified the different parts of the query, those tagged as having textual content are sent separately to Google Translation to get their translation using the option of automatic identification of the language provided. The service then returns the translations, together with the language identified.

For evaluation purposes, we applied the service included in the Google API to detect the language of each query in the sample. The service returns a list of languages for each input received, sorted by probability. We only keep the most probable language and discard the rest. For example, for the query *carteles de la guerra civil NOT "National Library of Spain"* we send to the service *carteles de la guerra civil* and *National Library of Spain* separately, and we receive Spanish and English respectively as the most probable languages.

The evaluation of this service is focused in two questions:

- Q1. Can we assume that the language of the query is Spanish when using the Spanish portal?
Q2. What is the effectiveness of the language identification service offered by Google?

In order to answer them, we manually annotated if the query is in Spanish (options are *Yes*, *No*, *N/A*), and the accuracy of the identification (*All languages were correctly identified*, *Part of the languages were correctly identified*, *None of the languages were correctly identified*, *N/A:operator or symbol*, *N/A:language hard to identify*).

Annotation, evaluation conducted and results are available at https://rnd-2.eanadev.org/home/mmarrero/experiments/crosslingual_SpanishPilot/evaluation.translations, and the excel sheet used to annotate is also available online at:

¹⁰

<https://pro.europeana.eu/post/improving-discoverability-with-new-entities-in-europeana-collections>

¹¹ Our best indicator for the language of the metadata, especially when no language tags are used on metadata values.

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/145ccK7yuvT3nAX9cVmefMeMf8Ni61LEt-v4V-VhWLj0/>

Q1. Can we assume that the language of the query is Spanish when using the Spanish portal?

The results obtained confirm a significant proportion of the queries to be not language-specific. In figure 2 and figure 3 we can see that in 37.7% of the cases there is no clear language to be identified. This can happen because the query is made out of operators (e.g., *:*) or because it is not clear what the correct language is, for example for named entities (e.g., Mozart). The latter is the most frequent reason, as can be seen in figure 2. In those cases, it is interesting to note that Google assigns the language fitting most the entity's real-world context to the entity. For example, *Coruña* is identified as a query in Galician, *Barcelona* as a query in Catalan, *Amsterdam* as a query in Dutch, and *Mozart* as a query in German.

Removing these cases, we can see in figure 2 that the number of queries in Spanish (with some degree of certainty) is twice the number of queries in other languages. Answering Q1, with such an assumption we would be failing in almost a quarter of the queries, while in 40% of the cases it would be unclear (although probably valid, as most entities are valid in many languages, also Spanish, as they were written).

Figure 2. Percentage of queries that are written in Spanish. Sample of 300 queries issued in the Europeana Spanish portal.

Q2. What is the effectiveness of the language identification service offered by Google?

Regarding Q2, figure 3 shows that the Google service correctly identifies the language in 93.6% of the language-specific queries (that is, 58.33% of all queries), and only fails totally or partially in a 6.4% of them (that is, 4.00% of all queries).

Figure 3. Language identification effectiveness obtained with Google Translation applied on a sample of 300 queries issued in the Europeana Spanish portal.

Real-time translation of search query

As explained in the previous section, the identification and translation of the queries is done in real-time using Google Translation when the source language is unknown.

To evaluate effectiveness, we applied the Google Translation service to the sample of queries, and we manually annotated the quality of the translations. We compared them with the translations obtained from the eTranslation service, using Spanish or the language identified by Google as source language. To evaluate efficiency, we computed the average time of response of Google Translation for a bigger sample of 13,138 queries collected from 1st December 2020 to 28th February 2021 (*sample_v1*, see *Annex C. Sampling*). We focused the evaluation on the following questions:

Q3. What is the most effective system, Google Translation or eTranslation?

Q4. Do we obtain better results by assigning Spanish as source language, or by using the automatic identification provided by Google?

Q5. Is ambiguity in queries an issue for translation? Is it common in Europeana queries?

Q6. Is the existence of typos in queries an issue for translation? Is it common in Europeana queries?

Q7. Is the existence of entities in queries an issue for translation? Is it common in Europeana queries?

Q8. How efficient is Google Translation in the identification plus translation of queries?

Annotation, evaluation conducted and results are available together with the data for the previous task, Real-time detection of search query language.

Q3. What is the most effective system, Google Translation or eTranslation?

In order to answer Q3, we simplified the annotations related to the accuracy of the translation for the different systems by grouping them as *ok*, *unclear*, *wrong*, and *error* (see *Annex B. Evaluation* for more information on the actual tags used). Table 1 shows that Google Translation is approximately 20% more effective than eTranslation, reaching a 72.6% when the source language is set to Spanish, and a slightly better result when using automatic language identification.

Q4. Do we obtain better results by assigning Spanish as source language, or by using the automatic identification provided by Google?

We can see in table 1 that the assignment of the source language does not have a clear impact on the general effectiveness of translation. However if we take only those 20.7% of queries that are not written in Spanish, translating them as if they were Spanish has a negative impact: 7 percentage points with Google, and 3 percentage points with

eTranslation (see table 2). The use of automatic identification with eTranslation is not straightforward though, as it raises an error when the language identified by Google is not supported (for example, Latin), which happened in 12.6% of the whole sample.

Table 1. Translation effectiveness obtained with Google Translation and eTranslation using as source language Spanish (*es*) or automatic identification (*auto*) when applied on a sample of 300 queries issued in the Europeana Spanish portal.

	ok	wrong	unclear	error	% ok
Google auto	220	47	33	-	73.3
Google es	218	49	33	-	72.6
eTranslation auto	159	80	23	38	53.0
eTranslation es	160	107	33	-	53.3

Table 2. Translation effectiveness obtained with Google Translation and eTranslation using as source language Spanish (*es*) or automatic identification (*auto*) when applied on queries written in a language different from Spanish.

	ok	wrong	unclear	error	% ok
Google auto	46	9	7	-	74.2
Google es	41	16	5	-	66.1
eTranslation auto	39	5	5	13	62.9
eTranslation es	37	20	5	-	59.7

Q5. Is ambiguity in queries an issue for translation? Is it common in Europeana queries?

In order to answer Q5, we indicated for each query if it is lexically ambiguous with different possible translations, that is, if it can have different translations depending on the intention of the user (e.g., *granada* could be a Spanish city but also a Latin American city, a country and island, an explosive artefact, or even fruit; *CUEVA PINTADA* can be an archaeological park with that name in Spanish or a general painted cave; *historia* can refer to history or a story). Ambiguous queries account for 9.3% of the queries. As expected, all the translations obtained from the ambiguous queries are annotated as not clear (because it depends on the intent of user), and only in a few cases they are wrong (see figure 4), indicating that this is not a feature that affects the quality of the

translation itself, but the relevance of the results retrieved with it, as we will see in the next section.

Figure 4. Impact of lexical ambiguity with different possible translations in the quality of the translation. Google Translation with language detection (top left), Google Translation with Spanish as source language (top right), eTranslation with language detection (bottom left), and eTranslation with Spanish as source language (bottom right).

Q6. Is the existence of typos in queries an issue for translation? Is it common in Europeana queries?

Another feature that can have an impact on the translation of the queries is the existence of typos. Only 5.3% of the queries contain typos (e.g., *womens*), and the quality

of translations is negatively affected by them (see table 3). In figure 5 we see that queries with typos can result in good, unclear or bad translations, with slightly more cases of unclear translations (and errors in the case of eTranslation with language detection, probably because the language identification service returned some rare languages for these cases, not supported by the service).

Table 3. Percentage of correct translation for queries with and without typos.

	%correct for queries with typos	%correct for queries w/o typos
Google auto	31.3	75.7
Google es	31.3	75.0
eTranslation auto	18.8	54.9
eTranslation es	31.3	54.6

Figure 5. Impact of typos in the quality of the translation. Google Translation with language detection (top left), Google Translation with Spanish as source language (top right), eTranslation with language detection (bottom left), and eTranslation with Spanish as source language (bottom right).

Q7. Is the existence of entities in queries an issue for translation? Is it common in Europeana queries?

The existence of entities is one of the main questions to solve in the context of Europeana, where it is expected that a good portion of the queries contain them. We annotated those queries with entities that should not be translated (e.g., *Juan Gris* can not be translated as *John Gray*, or *Antonio Sordi* as *Antonio Deaf*), and we discovered that 50.7% of the queries contain them, while in 6.7% of the cases it is not clear. In table 4 we can see there is an impact of this feature in translation, and figure 6 shows that, while many cases of queries with entities are correctly translated, most of the wrong translations obtained with Google Translation come from queries containing entities: more than 70% of the wrong cases are queries with entities. The effect is not so clear in the case of eTranslation, where 58% of the wrong cases are queries with entities.

Table 4. Percentage of correct translation for queries with or without entities that should not be translated, or where this is not clear.

	%correct for queries with entities	%correct when unclear	%correct for queries w/o entities
Google auto	71.7	10.0	85.2
Google es	72.4	10.0	82.8
eTranslation auto	50.7	10.0	62.5

eTranslation es	55.9	5.0	57.8
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Figure 6. Impact of entities in the quality of the translation. Google Translation with language detection (top left), Google Translation with Spanish as source language (top right), eTranslation with language detection (bottom left), and eTranslation with Spanish as source language (bottom right).

Q8. How efficient is Google Translation in the identification plus translation of queries?

Finally, we answer Q8 by calculating the time that Google Translation service takes to get the translation of a query, including the automatic identification of language. As the query may be splitted in different parts by the query parser, and they are sent independently to the translation service, we calculated the time per call as well as the time it takes to process a whole query on average. On average, each call takes 57.3, with

a standard deviation of 9.6 ms, while processing a whole query takes on average 62.2 and a standard deviation of 25.5 ms (see figure 7). The maximum time per call is 218 ms, while per query it can take up to 840 ms. The time to process a query can be reduced by using threads or batch calls (see *Annex D. Experiment 2* for more details).

Figure 7. Time to get the translation of a query when using Google Cloud Translation API with no source language provided.

Construction of multilingual search string

Once obtained the English translation of a query, the next step is the construction of the query or queries that will be issued on the Solr collection to retrieve multilingual results. In the Spanish pilot we have implemented a simple approach that consists in connecting those two queries, the original and the translation obtained with Google Translation, using the logical operator OR. One of the benefits of this approach is that the results retrieved with each query are already automatically merged according to the score obtained. As an example, the query *carteles de la guerra civil NOT "National Library of Spain"* is converted in the multilingual system to (*carteles de la guerra civil NOT "National Library of Spain"*) OR (*civil war posters NOT "National Library of Spain"*). Other options to build this query are open, for example considering querying only those fields in the index that are in the language of each one of the queries.

We tested this approach using the sample and conducted an evaluation to answer the following questions:

Q9. Do we retrieve more documents in total (potential difference in Recall)?

- Q10. Do we retrieve documents in other languages in the top ten positions?
- Q11. Is the relevance affected in the top ten positions (difference in P@10)?
- Q12. Does ambiguity have an impact on the top ten results?
- Q13. Do typos have an impact on the top ten results?
- Q14. Do entities have an impact on the top ten results?
- Q15. Are there other elements affecting relevance in the top ten positions?

In order to answer those questions, we searched in the Solr Metadata collection using the sample of queries and their corresponding multilingual queries, and we manually assessed the (binary) relevance of the documents that are retrieved by one system but not by the other in their top ten. We finally assessed the documents retrieved for 297 queries, as two of them are not valid queries and hence can not be parsed by the search engine, and a third one is unintelligible (*nullnull NOT "National Library of Spain"*).

Annotation, evaluation conducted and results are available at https://rnd-2.eanadev.org:/home/mmarrero/experiments/crosslingual_SpanishPilot/evaluation.search_retrieval, and the sheet used to annotate is also available online at: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1UK9pzUgQWy2WqAvk1K6XzcOvMh9MX7trmKtjFgksNe0/>. More information about the evaluation can be found in *Annex B. Evaluation*.

Q9. Do we retrieve more documents in total (potential difference in Recall)?

We obtained more results in 35.7% of the queries, with an average of 17,015 new documents found for them, and a median of 252 (in half of the cases the number of results is lower than this, while in half of the cases is higher, more than 300,000 in a few cases).

Figure 8. Number of new results retrieved by the multilingual system for those queries of the sample where the multilingual version retrieves more documents than the monolingual one.

In 35 queries (11.8%), the monolingual system did not retrieve any result. That number was reduced to 27 (9%) queries in the multilingual version, however the results were not relevant for those 8 new non-zero queries. It is expected that the multilingual system would help better in this scenario for more rare query languages, and also when the whole Solr collection is translated to English.

Q10. Do we retrieve documents in other languages in the top ten positions?

Considering the property *edm:language* as the language of the document¹², we got an average of 2.16 different languages per query in the top ten results when using the monolingual approach. That number increases only slightly to 2.30 in the multilingual approach. The short increase is explained by the fact that we already have documents in any language enriched with entities translated to multiple languages, Spanish among them. However, if we consider only English, we go from 1.43 to 1.84 documents in English on average (see figure 9), and the number of queries for which we have at least

¹² It is not always true that *edm:language* indicates the language of all original metadata in a record, but it is generally the best bet in the absence of complete language tagging of all metadata fields.

one document in English also increases from 97 to 128. These numbers are more representative of the benefits of the multilingual approach, and the increase will be higher once the whole Solr collection is translated to English (which is planned as future work in the Europeana multilingual strategy).

Figure 9. Distribution of documents in English (according to *edm:language*) per query retrieved in the monolingual vs the multilingual system. The mean of each distribution is displayed as a colored bar in the x-axis. Note that the real data is discrete - it is rendered as continuous by the visualization we chose.

Q11. Is the relevance affected in the top ten positions (difference in P@10)?

In 34.7% of the queries, the set of documents retrieved by the monolingual and the multilingual system in the top ten positions is different, with 11.7 documents on average per query that appear in only one of the systems. They sum up a total of 1203 documents whose relevance was manually assessed.

In most cases the precision is not affected when using the multilingual system (78.1% of the queries), in 13.5% of the cases the documents retrieved in the top ten positions are worse, and in 8.4% of the cases the documents are more relevant. As we can see in figure 10, in many cases the difference in Precision at 10 (P@10) is small, and on average it is -0.026, that is, we lose on average one document that is relevant in the top ten for one query out of four.

Figure 10. Difference in Precision at 10 for the sample of queries when comparing the monolingual and multilingual version.

Q12. Does ambiguity have an impact on the top ten results?

A regression analysis using ANOVA and linear models, indicates that lexical ambiguity with different possible translations has a significant effect on P@10 (F-value = 8.7324, P-value = 0.003378).

Figure 11. Number of the ambiguous and unambiguous queries that exhibit a given difference in P@10. The mean of each distribution is displayed as a colored bar in the x-axis.

Ambiguous queries account for 9.9% of the cases analyzed. None of them increased P@10, and in one third of those cases it decreased (see figure 11).

Q13. Do typos have an impact on the top ten results?

A regression analysis using ANOVA shows that the existence of typos in the queries do not seem to have an impact on the relevance of the top ten results (F-value = 0.3035, P-value = 0.5821). On average, both distributions are very similar (see figure 12), however the results with typos do not change the precision at all.

Figure 12. Number of the queries with and without typos that exhibit a given difference in P@10. The mean of each distribution is displayed as a colored bar in the x-axis.

Q14. Do entities have an impact on the top ten results?

A regression analysis using ANOVA and linear models indicates that the existence of non translatable entities in the queries has a significant effect on P@10 (F-value = 3.0714, P-value = 0.04785).

Figure 13. Number of the queries that exhibit a given difference in P@10 depending on the existence of non-translatable entities in the query.

More than half of the queries contain entities that should not be modified when translating them to English, and in more than 6% of the cases this is not clear. This usually happens with work titles with no clear English translation, but also with ambiguous queries like *granada*, which is valid as a city in Spanish and English, but should be translated to *grenade* when referring to the explosive artefact, or *pomegranate* when referring to the fruit. Only in one case the relevance in the top ten documents was improved (0.58%), while this happened in 23.76% of the cases when no entities were involved. When the queries contain entities, the precision is very similar on average to the precision obtained when they don't (see figure 13), however in the first case the precision is the same¹³ or worse, while in the latter there is more variability, with many cases where the precision has been improved. The precision is also negatively affected when the existence of entities is not clear, and in this case the average also reflects this. There is a clear dependency between these cases and the existence of ambiguity in the queries (e.g., *granada* is tagged as an entity only if it refers to the city, so this is tagged as *ambiguous*, and *not clear* for entities).

¹³ The reason could be that even though the translation may be incorrect, as indicated in Q7, it does not return additional results so the precision in those cases does not change.

Q15. Are there other elements affecting relevance in the top ten positions?

We run a manual analysis of those queries with a notable negative difference in precision at 10 (difference in P@10 \leq -0.5). We removed those queries which were ambiguous, contained typos or non-translatable entities, or were wrongly translated. We analyzed the resulting queries and discovered that for some of them the cause of bad results is linked to the lack of context. For example, *guerra civil* in the context of the Spanish portal probably refers to the *Spanish civil war* (and this is how it was annotated for the evaluation, see *Annex B. Annotation rules and observations*). In other cases, the problem is the lack of indication about the specific field. For example, the query *organista* (organist) matches photographs taken by Pavel Svoboda, who happens to be an organist. Finally, bad metadata as a consequence of wrong enrichments or vague descriptions could also lead to bad results. This is the case of the queries *futbol* (football), *deporte* (sport) or *alpinismo* (alpinism), where for the first one we found documents¹⁴ enriched correctly as *Sport* but wrongly as *Football* due to issues in the vocabulary used¹⁵, for the second one we found documents wrongly enriched with the concept *Sport*, and for the third one we found documents talking about pilgrimages¹⁶.

Summary and discussion

The first step in the process is the real-time translation of the query to English, which is used as a pivot language. This step requires the previous identification of the language of the query, and we used Google for this in the pilot. The evaluations conducted show that the accuracy in the identification of the language goes from two thirds to more than 90% when we use Google Translation instead of assuming the language is Spanish. Its impact on the accuracy of translation is however limited, and choosing always Spanish leads to a loss of less than 1 percentage point in average for the whole sample. Using Spanish as the source language of non-Spanish queries leads to a loss of accuracy of 8 percentage points in the case of Google Translation, and 3 percentage points when using eTranslation. The reason is that Spanish is a valid option for those queries where the language is not clear (e.g., person names), and in the remaining cases, most of the queries are already in English or in languages very similar to Spanish (e.g., Catalan). The use of automatic identification of language combined with eTranslation should be

¹⁴ For example, https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/0943101/libvar_ARTICLE_18116

¹⁵ Sport and Football are labels for the concept of sport at <http://vocabularies.unesco.org/thesaurus/concept7666>

¹⁶ For example, https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/92022/BibliographicResource_1000125936130 has "Climbing mountain" in its title, which is appropriate for the matter pictured but probably does not correspond to what a modern viewer would call "alpinism".

carefully considered if we want to identify and translate to English non-EU official languages, as it raises errors when they are not supported (that happened in 12.6% of the queries).

In terms of the translation, we implemented Google Translation in the pilot, and the evaluation showed that it is 20% more effective than eTranslation, with roughly 73% accuracy. In terms of efficiency, it takes an average of 62.2 ± 25.5 ms per query (we did not calculate the efficiency for eTranslation as it is an asynchronous service).

Once we have the translation of the query, the next step in the pilot is the construction of the multilingual query. For this, we connected the original and translated query using the logical operator *OR*. The evaluation conducted shows that we retrieve more documents in more than one third of the queries, with an average of 17,015 more documents per query. We also observed that the number of documents in English increased from 1.43 on average per query to 1.84 in the top ten, while the number of queries with at least one document in English in those positions increased 10 percentage points. This increase in recall is expected to have a negative impact on precision, however the evaluation indicates that its impact in the top ten results is small, with an average of approximately one relevant document lost in the top ten positions for one in four queries.

We additionally analyzed factors that could have a negative impact on the translations and the relevance of the results retrieved. The existence of lexical ambiguity in the queries with different possible translations accounts for 9% of the cases, and leads to unclear translations, and a significant negative effect on precision in the top ten results. The existence of entities that are not supposed to be modified when translated to English, which account for more than half of the cases, lead to most of the wrong translations when using Google. For these queries, precision is not improved and it even decreases in some cases. The existence of typos in the queries, which happens in 5% of the queries, does not have any significant impact on the precision. A manual analysis of the documents retrieved further identifies additional issues like the lack of context of the query and the existence of wrong enrichments in the collection. These issues are already present in the monolingual approach, but they are expected to be worsened in the multilingual approach. Table 5 contains a list of issues that negatively affect the search results, including the existence of lexical ambiguity with different possible translations (first row), and the existence of entities that should not be translated (rows 6 and 7). It also lists some possible remedial actions.

Table 5. Issues that negatively affect the search results in the multilingual approach, and possible actions to address them. The issues in blue have been tested, and the first one has a significant effect on the results.

Source	Explanation	Specific to new multilingual approach	Possible actions
Lexical ambiguity E.g., <i>Granada</i> as place, explosive artefact, or fruit	The intention of the user is not clear and multiple translations with different meaning are possible E.g., <i>Granada</i> and <i>not grenada</i> or <i>pomegranate</i>	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency (showing multilingual query to users) • Topic/Author filter • Search by field • Ranking by popularity
Lexical ambiguity E.g., <i>Granada</i> as region in Latin America or a city in Spain	The intention of the user is not clear but the translation is the same	No, but translations may also have this issue.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency (showing multilingual query to users) • Topic/Author filter • Search by field • Ranking by popularity
Handling of phrases. E.g. <i>ludoterapia</i> is correctly translated as <i>play therapy</i> which are two very common nouns that can appear in documents related to therapies in general.	The translation is a phrase, where the meaning may be different if the keywords do not appear together.	No, but the translated query may have this issue even though the original does not.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Account in the rank for closeness in the search keywords
Vagueness E.g., <i>civil war</i> is probably referring to <i>Spanish civil war</i> if queried from the Spanish portal	The translation is more generic, or the implicit information given by the user context is lost with it.	No, but the issue is worse when retrieving information in other languages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic/Author filter • Ranking by popularity (popularity depending on the language/portal)
Cross-language homonyms E.g., <i>home</i> is <i>man</i> in Catalan	Same or similar words with different meaning in different languages	No, but the issue may be worse when all the metadata is translated to English.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filter by language • Topic/Author filter • Route queries to fields in that specific language
Entities that should not be translated E.g., ' <i>Antonio Sordi</i> ' is not ' <i>Antonio Deaf</i> '	The name of the entity is already valid in English	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of knowledge graphs.

Entities that should not be translated <i>E.g., some titles like 'glossa ordinaria'</i>	Translation to English do not exists	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of knowledge graphs.
Entities that should be translated in a very specific way <i>E.g., 'Dos metros lejos de ti' -> 'five feet apart'</i>	Translation to English is not literal	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of knowledge graphs.
Wrong enrichments. <i>E.g., metadata related to water sports is tagged as 'football'.</i>	Due to issues during the enrichment process or because issues in the vocabulary used, enrichments can be wrong.	No, but most enrichments contain English tags, so the problem will become more visible.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement in the enrichment process. • Validation of enrichments.

Conclusions

The Spanish pilot is a working prototype that has progressed in the line of the multilingual search strategy by implementing several processes contemplated in it: the real-time translation of the query, including the identification of the language, and the construction and use in search of a multilingual query. The prototype works with the whole Solr Metadata collection, which contains more than 62 million Cultural Heritage objects in multiple languages. Those objects are expected to be translated to English and indexed in the search engine in future versions, following the Europeana Multilingual Strategy.

The pilot has shown the feasibility of applying a multilingual information retrieval system in Europeana, given our current data and technical possibilities. It obtains a reasonable performance when using Google Translation API for the language identification and translation of the queries in real-time. The number of documents retrieved increases considerably, as well as the number of English documents retrieved in the top ten positions, while the relevance in those positions is not affected significantly. The evaluation conducted further assesses the impact in the quality of the results retrieved, and analyzes some of the decisions adopted in order to guide the following steps.

The evaluation conducted shows a better effectiveness of Google over eTranslation in terms of translation quality, and reflects a high accuracy in the identification service provided by Google, as opposed to the use of the language of the portal as source

language of the query. Although the impact of assuming one language or the other for the source query is not very high in the quality of the translations obtained, it is still relevant to get high accuracy on language detection for the display (which is not covered in this report, but still part of the pilot) and poses less potential risks for other Europeana language-specific portals, where users may not use the expected language according to their chosen portal.

The evaluation also confirmed two issues already covered in the literature as well as in a previous experiment with Europeana data (Marrero et al. 2021): the lexical ambiguity of the queries has a bad impact on the search results, and the queries with entities that should not be translated lead to bad translations and hence, bad search results. The use of a different query language than the one originally used also leads to additional issues: a) documents in the original language may have a higher probability of being more relevant for some queries, b) there are more enrichments described in English, and hence the probability of finding bad enrichments is higher. These issues, together with others measures to increase precision in regular monolingual systems, should be addressed before adopting a multilingual search information retrieval system wide scale, when the probability of getting more noisy results is higher given the use of translations to English in the Solr collection, and the language identification and translation of the query in not so common languages.

Future work

The next steps in terms of the multilingual strategy contemplate the translation of the whole Solr collection to English. The first step will be the translation of the metadata, which is currently addressed by the ongoing project *Europeana Translate*¹⁷.

As a result of the evaluation conducted, we will address the poor quality of translations obtained for the entities which should not be translated, as they represent a big portion of the queries at Europeana. In a short term, we will probably disable the translation for this type of queries, while in a medium term we will see the feasibility of identifying those entities in a controlled vocabulary, so we can take from there the required translations. This is already contemplated in the multilingual strategy, and the steps taken here can also benefit the translation of the metadata and full text content of the Europeana collections (and the other way around), where multiple entities are expected to appear.

¹⁷ <https://pro.europeana.eu/project/europeana-translate>

The Spanish pilot is expected to be in production at the beginning of 2022, and then a user oriented evaluation can take place. This may be the opportunity to explore ways to limit the issues related to the different types of ambiguity of the queries. Some options to address this include a) being transparent with the users about the multilingual query generated, so that they can detect and maybe correct wrong translations, b) extending the existing facets (and adapting them to the multilingual interface) so users can further filter the search results by topic, creator, language, etc. (improvement M-F3 as described in the Europeana search improvement strategy¹⁸), c) offering more flexibility to the users regarding the specific fields to be used in the search (improvement M-F14), and d) including a popularity criteria in the ranking (improvement M-F9 and M-F10, which may also include popularity criteria based on the language/portal in order to address the vagueness issue as described in table 5).

In general, the approach would also benefit from taking general measures to reduce noise, like improving the precision of the current enrichment (already ongoing, and also part of the search strategy as ES-F9), taking the closeness of the search keywords in the documents into consideration in the rank (improvement M-F8), and testing different approaches in the construction of the multilingual query, as for example using only language specific fields. The latter will help to prevent matching keywords with different meanings in other languages (e.g., *home* refers to man in Catalan).

Finally, we also aim to evaluate this approach for queries from Europeana portals in other languages, to decide if it can be safely extended to them.

Bibliography

Agosti, M., Fabris, E., Silvello, G.: On synergies between information retrieval and digital libraries. In: Proceedings of the Italian Research Conference on Digital Libraries, 2019. pp. 3–17. Pisa, Italia (2019)

Chen, H.: Digital library research in the US: an overview with a knowledge management perspective. *Program: Electronic Library and Information Systems* 38 (3), 157–167 (2004)

Diekema, A.R.: Multilinguality in the digital library: A review. *The Electronic Library* 30 (2), 165–181 (2012)

Dolamic, L., Savoy, J.: Retrieval effectiveness of machine translated queries. *Journal of the American Society for Information Sciences & Technology* 6, 2266–2273 (2010)

España-Bonet, C., Stiller, J., Ramthun, R., van Genabith, J., Petras, V.: Query translation for

¹⁸ M-F3: Extend faceting and filtering. Europeana DSI-4 Search Improvement Strategy. Accessible at: <https://pro.europeana.eu/post/europeana-search-strategy>

cross-lingual search in the academic search engine PubPsych. In: Research Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research. pp. 37–49. Limassol, Cyprus (2018)

Kools, J., Lagos, N., Petras, V., Stiller, J., Vald, E.: GALATEAS project (Generalized Analysis of Logs for Automatic Translation and Episodic Analysis of Searches). D7.4 Final Evaluation of Query Translation (2013), version 2.0

Marrero M., Isaac A., Freire N. (2021) Automatic Translation and Multilingual Cultural Heritage Retrieval: A Case Study with Transcriptions in Europeana. In: Berget G., Hall M.M., Brenn D., Kumpulainen S. (eds) Linking Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries. TPDFL 2021. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 12866. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-86324-1_17. Full report accessible at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5497842>

Matusiak, K.K., Meng, L., Barczyk, E., Shih, C.J.: Multilingual metadata for cultural heritage materials: The case of the tse-tsung chow collection of chinese scrolls and fan paintings. *The Electronic Library* 33 (1), 136–51 (2015)

Oudenaren, J.V.: The World Digital Library. *Uncommon Culture* 3 (5/6), 65–71 (2012)

Peters, C., Braschler, M., Clough, P.: *Multilingual Information Retrieval: From Research to Practice*. Springer, Heidelberg, Germany (2012)

Savoy, J., Braschler, M.: *Information Retrieval Evaluation in a Changing World: Lessons Learned from 20 Years of CLEF*, chap. Lessons Learnt from Experiments on the Ad Hoc Multilingual Test Collections at CLEF, pp. 177–200. Springer, Cham, Switzerland (2019)

Stiller, J., Gade, M., Petras, V.: Ambiguity of queries and the challenges for query language detection. In: *CLEF 2010 LABs and Workshops* (2010). Padua, Italy (2010)

Stiller, J., Gade, M., Petras, V.: Multilingual access to digital libraries: The Europeana Use Case. *Information. Wissenschaft & Praxis* 64 (2-3), 86–95 (2013)

Stiller, J., Petras, V.: Best practices for multilingual access. Tech. rep., Europeana (2016), available At <https://pro.europeana.eu/post/best-practices-for-multilingual-access>

Stiller, J., Petras, V., Luschow, A.: *CLUBS Project (Cross-Lingual Bibliographic Search)*. M5.3 Final Evaluation (2019), version 1.0

Vassilakaki, E., Garoufallou, E.: Multilingual digital libraries: A review of issues in system-centered and user-centered studies, information retrieval and user behavior. *The International Information & Library Review* 45, 3–19 (2013)

Annex A. Additional documentation

Spanish Search Pilot. Mónica Marrero. January-August 2021. Available at:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1hi2gZXrTRTNAS2hqz8VZIDu4vHKAv1RVuxRtWjOpbVM>

MS3 Outcomes of multilingual experiments, and their contribution to the multilingual strategy. Antoine Isaac, Dasha Moskalenko, Mónica Marrero, Valentine Charles, Julia Schellenberg. 24 Sept 2021. Available at:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TtBFlyzVg84Z1xjNcWjV_V2KxmWlXqKo/

Addressing multilingual challenges at Europeana: An update focusing on item display and (Spanish) search. Mónica Marrero, Dasha Moskalenko, Antoine Isaac, Hugo Manguinas. Europeana Foundation Explainer. 20 Oct 2021. Available at:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1pyzSSRCOqEq-TyBGW16MOvAv7IcPYRovpyK11sK0gMk/>

Addressing multilingual challenges at Europeana: An update. Antoine Isaac and Mónica Marrero. DCMI Virtual 2021. 13 Oct 2021.

https://www.dublincore.org/conferences/2021/presentations/addressing_multilingual_challenges_at_europeana_an_update/ Slides available at:

<https://www.slideshare.net/antoineisaac/addressing-multilingual-challenges-at-europeana-an-update-dcmi-2021>

Annex B. Annotation (evaluation) rules and observations

Query characteristics, language identification and translation quality

General rules

- Operators are only considered for the question about the parsing (e.g., in the query *Mongrell y Torrent, José NOT DATA_PROVIDER:"CER.ES: Red Digital de Colecciones de museos de España"*, the author and provider are considered for the translation, but not the operators "NOT" and "DATA_PROVIDER:").
- Use of uppercase and tildes (or lack of) are not considered typos (these elements do not have any impact in the search as they are normalized, and do not seem to have any impact in the quality of the translation either).

Rules for quality of language identification

- For locations and person names, we annotate as *N/A: language hard to identify (e.g. named entity)* if it does not need translation. Otherwise, it is considered language dependent. This is not always clear nonetheless (e.g. *Cordoba* can be translated as *Cordova* or left it as it is).
- Titles are considered language dependent.

Rules for quality of translation

- The quality of the translation is bad if the query should not be translated.
- Entities like locations and person names should be translated when there is an English version of it.
- Titles should be translated only when there is a recognized translation in English for that title, which may or not match with a literal translation (e.g., *piratas de roma* is a Spanish title with apparently no correspondence in English, so it should be left as it is. If it is translated to *pirates of rome* then we can consider the quality of translation as *none of the meaning was transferred*).
- Conjunctions in entities should be translated according to the previous rules: if there is evidence for translating the conjunction in English (e.g., *Mogrell y Torrent* is translated as *Mogrell and Torrent* if there is evidence the translation references the same entity).
- If the query should NOT be translated (e.g., book title), the analysis of the translation is wrong if it has been translated.
- If some words in the translation are correct, the quality of the annotation is *Part of the meaning was transferred*.
- Provider names should be translated except when there is no (semi) official translation available for that entity (e.g. *Fotografia Unal* should be left as it is).

Observations

- Google identifies the language of an entity as that one closer to the entity context (e.g., *Mozart* is tagged as German language).
- When the query does not match with the language identified, it is frequent the translation services tested leave the query unchanged or very slightly changed. For example, *la febre d'or* could be the gold rush or a novel with the same title in Catalan. With Spanish as source language, Google and eTranslation translated it as *the febre d'or*, while with Catalan as source language it was translated into *the gold rush* by Google.
- The translation services tested usually translate the connector in entities even when the entity should not be translated (e.g. *Hauser y Menet*, *Angel Pardo y Puzo*).
- When only some parts of the translation are correct and we annotate the quality as *Part of the meaning was transferred*, the words not related to the query in the translation may be very harmful for the search. This is the case for example of *Leonardo da Vinci* translated by eTranslation as *Leonardo to win*. For future work, perhaps we could consider that 'parts' should not split named entities or complex lemmas. I.e. *oil paintings of Leonardo da Vinci* would be partially correct if either *oil paintings* and *Leonardo da Vinci* have been translated correctly.
- It is questionable whether we should translate locations in Latin. Following the rules, we should translate them if there is an English translation for it, but we need to make sure we also retain the original form in the multilingual query as an alternative. Same happens with entities for which different versions are valid in English (e.g., Minorca vs Menorca).
- eTranslation give very unexpected results in multiple cases:
 - Addition of *Mr.* to person names (e.g., *Adolphe Smith* is translated as *Mr. Adolphe Smith*).
 - Wrong assumptions (e.g., *CUEVA PINTADA* is translated as *Guinea-Fowl cave* while Google translates it as *painted cave*, which would be more neutral).
 - Very unexpected results when the input language is wrong (e.g., *spain* is translated to *Belgium* when the source language is set up to Spanish).
- Google translates roman numerals in centuries into arabic ones: *S.XIX* is translated to *19th century*.
- In some cases we obtain synonyms from different translation services. This happens with the query *Primera guerra mundial*, translated as *First World War* by Google, and as *World War I* by eTranslation. Both are correct, but it would be better if we could normalize the translation of these relevant concepts with the use of controlled vocabularies.

Relevance of search results

When the intention of the user is not clear¹⁹, the documents considered relevant are those that respond to the most specific information needs given the Europeana context and the Spanish context (given that the query was issued from the Europeana Spanish portal). Some examples are described in table 6.

Table 6. Examples of possible information needs and the one we selected

ID	QUERY	Alternative information needs	Information need adopted
11	granada	Explosive artefact, fruit, town or district in Latin America, city in Spain	City in Spain
32	CUEVA PINTADA	Specific arqueological park in Spain, any painted cave	Specific arqueological park in Spain http://www.cuevapintada.com
27	trabajo infantil	General concept of child labour, child labour in the Spanish context	General concept of child labour (as this is not specially relevant in the Spanish context and different from other countries).
36	guerra civil	Any civil war, Spanish civil war	Spanish civil war (as this is very relevant in the Spanish context).
188	scacchi	Person name, <i>bump</i> in Italian	Person name (considering the Europeana context).
234	las causas	General philosophical concept of 'cause', book title <i>Libro de las causas (Liber de causis)</i> .	Book title (given Europeana context) https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Liber_de_causis
278	los planetas	Planets in the Universe, Spanish rock group	Spanish rock group (as it is a well-known musical group in Spain).
298	Danzantes NOT "National Library of Spain"	Any dancing figure, specific reliefs in Monte Alban (considered a relevant piece of the Mesoamerican Art).	Specific reliefs in Monte Alban (considering the Europeana context).

¹⁹ Note that this does not necessarily mean the query could have different translations, but also different meanings given the same translation (e.g., *civil war* could refer to the Spanish civil war or any other).

Of course, this rule is not clear in all cases and it clearly depends on the interpretation of the annotator. For example, *lotería de navidad* is considered as the Spanish Christmas lottery, however *navidad* is considered as the general concept of Christmas. Both could be relevant events in the context of Spain, however the first one seems to be a very relevant event in Spain, different from the one in other countries.

Annex C. Additional technical details

Sampling

We took queries from the current Spanish portal (*page URL* starts with */es/search* OR */es/collections*) from 1 Dec 2020 to 28 Feb 2021. Note that we use *page URL* as a dimension, so the same query can appear more than once. Given that Google Analytics samples the data when it is above a threshold²⁰, we limit this effect by downloading the queries month by month and then properly joining the results. From this data, we removed those queries with 'total unique searches' = 0²¹. As a result we obtained **38,751** entries that resulted in **34,902** different queries (different query string -other parameters in the URL could be different-).

	Total queries	Most repetitive query	Occurrence
December 2020	16445 (18.18% total)	[empty query]	55
January 2021	13013 (14.67% total)	propaganda	73
February 2021	13024 (15.11%)	[empty query]	43

We got a stratified subsample of these queries (*subsample_strata*): we took the 100 most frequent queries as the *head* strata, a sample of 100 queries from the long-tail with frequency 1 as the *tail* strata, and then we took a weighted sample of 100 queries from the remaining ones as the *body* strata, using the frequency as weight.

We also generated an alternative sample of the data (*subsample_representative*) which takes a weighted sample of 300 queries using the frequency as weight. This sample was not used in the evaluation conducted but it can be found in the data.

In terms of the format, we saved the original data coming from Google Analytics in *xlsx* files, and converted it later to *csv* in order to process it. For other steps in the processing we may also have the same file duplicated in format *csv* and *xlsx*. In those cases the reason is that in order to upload it to Google docs, we need the *xlsx* because the quotes are not properly imported when using *csv* directly.

²⁰ In the first try, *sample_v1*, we got 13,138 different queries with at least one unique search (they actually had a minimum of three unique searches as result of the sampling made by Google Analytics).

²¹ It is not clear why this happens. It could be that some queries are activated using the link directly, but this is not clear either for the Service Experience team.

Prototype API

The live code used in the prototype is available in a private repository (<https://github.com/marrerom/emodules>), shared with the Europeana API team. A release (*0.1-alpha*) was created with the code used for the Search API. Other changes were implemented later, all of them for evaluation purposes (e.g., to get translations from the eTranslation system).

The content of parameters q and fq in Solr request need to be translated, however for the moment, only q is translated. Ticket for implementation in test API: <https://europeana.atlassian.net/browse/EA-2545>

Google Cloud Translation API

- 2nd March 2021: initiated trial period (90 days) in Google Cloud Translation API (advanced mode) with an individual account.
- 21st May 2021: official Europeana trial started with the developers account.

CEF Translation service (eTranslation) API

No connection with the eTranslation API was implemented in the first release (*0.1-alpha*), so it is not included in the Search API for the prototype. It has been used only for generating the translations to be evaluated. This is an asynchronous service, so the code developed for the purpose of evaluation calls the service, returns as translation the identification of the file where it is contained, and then replaces that identifier with the content of those files. The eTranslation service client is available at <https://github.com/nfreire/europeana-ettranslation-research>. The client and the service (ettranslation-callback) listening to receive them is deployed in <https://rnd-2.eanadev.org:/opt/tomcat/webapps>. The files with the translations are available at <https://rnd-2.eanadev.org:/var/lib/ettranslation>.

Query parser

The query can not be sent as a whole to the language identification or translation service, as it may contain operators, and different parts of the query can respond to different information needs and even different languages. In order to solve this we have implemented a query parser as part of the prototype API. This piece of software does the following:

- Detects operators to prevent sending them to the identification/translation service (e.g. 'AND', '+', '[field]:'). This will reduce noise and prevent removing/changing them unexpectedly.
- Detects sequences of words that are expected to be part of the same sentence

- so they are sent together to the identification/translation service.
- Add brackets to words affected by a unary operator so the whole translation received for that word is also affected by the same operator (e.g. *+cortauñas* could result in *+nail clipper*, where the operator is affecting only the first word, so we add brackets to the whole translation received: *+(nail clipper)*). This is actually a frequent error users make in the original queries, so only the first keyword is searched in that specific field.
 - Identify each part of the query as textual or not. Only textual parts (those with no operators) are sent to the identification or translation service.

For the Spanish Pilot this functionality has been implemented ad-hoc with regular expressions. For production versions it may be worth considering using directly the parser configured in Solr for the Metadata collection, which will make the application more robust although also more dependent on the specific search configuration (there are several query parsers available in Solr) and maybe less efficient.

Evaluation

Identification of the language and translation evaluation

We evaluated the quality of the identification of the language and translation via the script *script_v3_language&translations.r*, available at https://rnd-2.eanadev.org/home/mmarrero/experiments/crosslingual_SpanishPilot/analysis_retrieval_translation

That script takes as input the results obtained from the manual annotation done in the spreadsheet *Spanish Pilot. Translation*, available from the repository at https://rnd-2.eanadev.org/home/mmarrero/experiments/crosslingual_SpanishPilot/evaluation.translations/2.evaluation, and online at <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/145ccK7yuvT3nAX9cVmefMeMf8Ni61LEt-v4V-VhWLJ0/>

In order to make the analysis easier, we transformed the manual annotations given for the quality of translation of each system (i.e., Google or eTranslation, and using automatic language identification or Spanish as source) according to the rules in table 7. Important to note that, according to these rules, those translations where none of the meaning or only part of the meaning was transferred are considered *wrong*, and in case of ambiguous queries (i.e., queries for which different translations are possible) the quality of the translation is considered *unclear* unless it had been annotated as an error or a clearly wrong or partially wrong translation.

Table 7. Rules applied to the annotation of the quality of the translation in order to get simplified annotations (ok, wrong, unclear, error) for the evaluation.

Manual annotation	Simplified annotation
All meaning was transfered	ok
(Not translated OR Only change in letter case) AND (Translatable = No (English) OR Translatable = No (other reasons))	
None of the meaning was transfered	wrong
Part of the meaning was transfered	
(Not translated OR Only change in letter case) AND Translatable = Yes	
Not clear	unclear
(Not translated OR Only change in letter case OR All meaning was transferred) AND (Not clear OR ambiguous = Yes)	
Translation error	error

Search results evaluation

We evaluated the impact of the multilingual query in the search results using the script *script_v3_retrieval.r*, available at

https://rnd-2.eanadev.org/home/mmarrero/experiments/crosslingual_SpanishPilot/analysis_retrieval_translation. This script takes as input the manually annotated information

regarding the queries and quality of identification of language and translations, contained in the spreadsheet *Spanish Pilot. Translation*, as well as the information required to calculate the difference in Precision at 10 (P@10) between the monolingual and the multilingual system for each query in the sample. This information is contained in the files *P10_original.txt* and *P10_option1.txt*, explained below, and available at

https://rnd-2.eanadev.org/home/mmarrero/experiments/crosslingual_SpanishPilot/evaluation.translations/3.evaluation

In order to get this information we first set up the search engine and collection to be used. It was created on 21 of June 2021, and it is a almost a replica of the Solr search engine and Metadata collection in production that day, with only two changes in the configuration or the way the search is done in Solr respect to how this is done in Europeana portal:

- New fields text.en and text.es are added to the Solr schema. These fields collect all the data already copied into the existing field text (the default field used for search) that is tagged with the corresponding language, English (en) or Spanish (es). (e.g., proxy_dc_title.* is copied to text, while proxy_dc_title.en is copied to text.en, and proxy_dc_title.es is copied to text.es). The only exception is proxy_edm_type which does not have a language version, so it is also copied as such in text.en and text.es. The fields copied to text, as well as the percentage of items in Spanish and English can be seen in the document *Spanish Pilot. Statistics language tagged values in searchable fields* available at https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Jz_DcLeFXI2_u4CHmflyjMsjmfwbwXL4AV_CVe6ZYY1AA/
- Elevation is disabled when searching (enableElevation=false), as it will generally no longer work for the multilingual search²², so we could not compare the results with the monolingual version. The sorting however follows the same rules as in the Portal (that is, sorting applied in the Search API at the moment of the evaluation: "has_media" desc, "score" desc, "timestamp_update" desc, "europeana_completeness" desc, "europeana_id" asc).

The Solr search engine and the collection indexed are available at http://reindex.eanadev.org:9393/solr/#/search_test

Once the search engine and collection is indexed, we then collected the top ten retrieved results obtained with the original queries in the sample, and also with their corresponding multilingual queries²³. Due to the required effort to manually annotate the results, we limited the evaluation to the difference in P@10 between the two approaches²⁴. This way we just had to annotate those documents that differ in the top ten results when using the original query and the multilingual query.

The results obtained from the searches are available at https://rnd-2.eanadev.org:/home/mmarrero/experiments/crosslingual_SpanishPilot/evaluation.search_retrieval/2.output and are also online in the document *Spanish Pilot. Retrieval*, available at

²² For the elevation to work, the query must match exactly with the entries in the elevation.xml file. In the multilingual version, the query is extended so it won't match. E.g. if we have 'mesa' in the elevation file as query, and we query by '(mesa) OR (table)' then there is no match.

²³ We additionally collected the search results obtained for a third option we called *option2*, where the multilingual query is built as follows: (original query) OR (text.en: translated query). These options for building the multilingual query are included in the presentation *Spanish Search Pilot*. Mónica Marrero. January-August 2021, listed in Annex A.

²⁴ Another possibility is the use of Minimal Test Collections (MTC) but this approach requires more annotations. Paper available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1148170.1148219>

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1MSZ-Rwp_82c0JoDcOk8eiQMP8lJrjihKmWD5L_EFdBg/²⁵

We annotated a total of 1213 documents, indicating their binary relevance for the query and the confidence of the annotator as high, medium or low. We did not consider in the evaluation the results of three queries (queries with ids 105, 183 and 253) as two of them are not valid queries and hence can not be parsed by the search engine, and a third one is unintelligible (*nullnull NOT "National Library of Spain"*).

The manual annotation was done using the spreadsheet *Spanish pilot. Retrieval. Documents to assess relevance for option 1*, available at <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1UK9pzUgQWy2WqAvk1K6XzcOvMh9MX7trmKtjFgksNe0/>, and also at https://rnd-2.eanadev.org/home/mmarrero/experiments/crosslingual_SpanishPilot/evaluation.search_retrieval/3.evaluation

In order to calculate the difference in P@10, we then generated the two required files for *trec_eval*:

- The *results* files, with the top ten results per query and system that only appear in the monolingual or multilingual system.
- The *qrels* file, with only those documents from the ones contained in *results* that are considered relevant by the annotators.

The results obtained by *trec_eval* are stored in the documents *P10_original.txt* for the monolingual version, and *P10_option1.txt* for the multilingual version. It is important to note that these numbers do not mean anything by themselves, as it is the difference between P@10 that we are calculating with this process, and not the real P@10.

²⁵ Directly in the spreadsheet, via scripts, we additionally obtained the edm:language value of each document retrieved, in order to calculate metrics about the multilinguality of the search results. The reason is that this information was required later in the evaluation so it was not generated automatically by the software.

Annex D. Preliminary experiments

Before the main experiment reported in this document, some experiments were conducted in order to test the feasibility of the approach and detect possible issues to fix. The data regarding these preliminary experiments is available at https://rnd-2.eanadev.org:/home/mmarrero/experiments/crosslingual_SpanishPilot/preliminary_experiments.

Experiment 1

Data and resources

We used the whole sample obtained from Google Analytics in the first try (*sample_v1*). We applied the query parser developed to each query, and then sent each part identified by the parser to the Google Cloud Translation API the translation of the query using automatic language detection. For each query, we collected the results of the parsing, the translation obtained, and the time consumed by the parsing and the translation processes.

Output

- Query
- Parsing result
- Translation
- Parsing time (ms)
- Translation time (ms)
- Total time (ms)

Available online at:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/12jKi-e4M0Xn9Kc8S1GjV5ck7y48G-0eHOGcfSrrI99s/edit#gid=2105506504>

Processing time

The average time to translate is **98.46** milliseconds (the parsing time is 0 or 1 milliseconds at most in only a few cases). Each query can require several calls to the translation service as it may be composed of several different sentences. The total amount of time is proportional to the number of calls. This can be solved in several ways: a) making parallel translations, b) making a 'batch' call to Google (not sure all services would support this), c) sending all sentences as one with the proper delimiters (it has to be done ad-hoc for each translation service).

Issues found

1. Translation: Translation entities ok, except for those that can be also considered common words (e.g. 'Granada' is translated as 'grenade', no matter if the query is in upper or lower case).
2. Translation: 'Hispania' is translated as 'Spain', and 'carthagene' is translated as 'cartagena'
3. Translation: should we translate the content of some fields? Dataset names, ids, etc. This problem is not a big issue for Google because it does not translate strings that are not recognized as words, even if they are connected by '_' (e.g. '9200378_Ag_EU_TEL_a1230_Biblioteca' is not changed).
4. Translation: some things should not be translated at all (e.g. 'Aravo Oi/laridu(m) / Licin(i) f/[il(io)] a(nnorum) LI h(oc) l(oco) s(itus)')
5. Translation: autodetect fails sometimes (e.g. 'Av. Callao' - a famous street in Madrid - is considered Swedish and translated as 'Of. Callao').
6. Parsing: symbols are also sent to the service (e.g. commas) as they are part of the text to be translated. However it could be that it is a regular expression and then the risk is to lose them in the translation (e.g. '*:*' is translated as '*:*', '*:*gitano' is translated as '*:*Gypsy'). This is not the case in general for Google translate, but it could be for other translation services. Also, in some cases it does change the input: e.g. '*:*archivo aragón' is translated as '*: * aragon file', 'te?t' is translated as 'te? t'. **Having the characters '/', '\ and specially '?' as part of a regex is a problem for regular users.**
7. Parsing: regular text taken as field when followed by ":" (e.g. 'FITNESS REVOLUCIONARIO: LECCIONES ANCESTRALES PARA UNA SALUD SALVAJE' is translated as 'FITNESS REVOLUCIONARIO: (LESSONS) ANCESTRALS FOR WILD HEALTH'). We can detect only supported fields but then this functionality will be dependent on the configuration in Solr. **This issue, together with 3, could lead to deciding not to translate the content of fields when this operator is used.**
8. Parsing: error in following queries:
 - a. "los siete infantes de lara" YEAR:[1600 TO 1800] -> the seven infants of lara YEAR:([1600) TO 1800]
 - b. 10 / 5000 Resultados de traducción Kurtisane -> 10/5000 Kurtisane translation results
 - c. Tête-à-tête -> [Tête-à, -, tête]
 - d. Teoría de la conspiración: ¿Aterrizamos en la luna? -> [Teoría de la conspiració, n:, ¿Aterrizamos en la luna?]

Actions

- Issue 6. Find a simple solution to alleviate it. As a side effect, this will also break the sentence into more pieces to be sent to the translation service. [Fixed: any keyword containing special characters - not only regular expressions but also symbols to indicate boosting - is considered non-translatable text. Special characters are * ? \ ^ / ~]
- Issue 8. Fix. [Fixed: brackets content considered non-translatable text, included support to Unicode in character classes]
- Issue 9. Add measure of time for each translation call [Fixed]
- Technical: CSV file delimiter can not be tab, as it is used in a handful of queries [Fixed: replaced tab by space in queries for logging purposes. Note: import first in local in XLSX format before uploading to Google Excel sheets, as it removes the quotes].
- Technical: include portal and unique searches besides original query in logging [Fixed].
- Generate subsample to manually assess translation [Done in preliminar experiment 3 below]
- **Issues 6 and 7 remain.**

Experiment 2

Data and resources

Same data and resources experiment 1. This time we also compute the translation time **per call** to the translation service (Google Cloud in this case), as one query may require more than one call (one per each textual part it contains).

Output

- Query
- Parsing result
- Translation
- Parsing time (ms)
- Translation time (ms)
- Total time (ms)
- Time per call (ms) [in a different sheet]

Available online at:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1pQp1eww9LuQBH4-sHdMQZMonjhVEZfhu7yA5wL2Kww/edit#gid=64846505>

	Time per call (ms)	Time per query (ms)
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Average	57.25282247	62.19573912
Max	218	840
Min	47	0
STDEV	9.640994673	25.53515947

The increase in time per call does not seem to respond to a bigger amount of characters. The time per query increases proportionally to the number of different pieces to be sent to the translation service, although in most cases this is only one call.

Experiment 3

Data and resources

After fixing issues detected in previous experiments, we included the field *languages* to collect the most probable language identified by Google Cloud Translation API, and we used the same API for the translation of the queries using that language as source (automatic language identification). This time we used the whole sample of queries that will be used in the final evaluation (*sample_v2*). We also created a stratified subsample of 175 queries, with the initial idea of analyzing the quality of the translations but this was finally done with a different subsample for the final evaluation. The subsample was taken from the first sample (*sample_v2*) we obtained from Google Analytics, and it contains 75 queries among those with higher frequency (*head*), 50 among those with lower frequency (*tail*), and 50 among those with medium frequency (*body*). The strata of the query is also included in the output.

Output

- Query: content of parameter 'query'
- Count: 'total unique searches' according to Google Analytics. For the subsample, the queries are grouped by the query terms and then the sum of 'total unique searches' is calculated in the count.
- Stratum: head, body and tail groups according to the count (in descending order).
- Parsing: the different parts of the query, where only those that contain text are sent to the translation service.
- Translation: translated query (parts of the query translated and joined back together).
- Languages: language detected for each textual part of the query resulting from the parsing. The language displayed is the one with more confidence according to Google.

Results available for the whole sample:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1lsCtk1yAhX9F8GLyoyZRUecMkk90zejRffZ0qIMXgrw/edit#gid=545925011>

Results available for the subsample:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1_jmzley55omqkUScX7ntwz6s9YsAQs_ZmAffXQjeZw/edit#gid=0

Experiment 4

Data and resources

For this experiment, we used the sample used in the final evaluation (*sample_v2*) and we applied Google Cloud Translation API for the translation of the queries using Spanish as source language.

Output

- Query: content of parameter 'query'
- Count: 'total unique searches' according to Google Analytics. For the subsample, the queries are grouped by the query terms and then the sum of 'total unique searches' is calculated in the count.
- Stratum: head, body and tail groups according to the count (in descending order).
- Parsing: the different parts of the query, where only those that contain text are sent to the translation service.
- Translation: translated query (parts of the query translated and joined back together).
- Languages: language detected for each textual part of the query resulting from the parsing. The language displayed is the one with more confidence according to Google. In this experiment, this language is not used for the translation.

Available online at:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1INizoYHvPntgRJ8qTLmQXyHRfKWC5S3hZjzgg_n1HIPA/